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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SITE-SPECIFIC
MICROSPHERE IN CORPORATED GEL OF DOXYCYCLINE
HYCLATE FOR PERIODONTITIS**¹Reshma.B*, ²Shamna Mole S*Department of Pharmaceutics, Mookambika College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, and Research,
Muvattupuzha, Ernakulam, Kerala.**Abstract**

Periodontitis is an inflammatory disease of the supporting tissues of the teeth caused by groups of specific microorganisms. Periodontitis involves progressive loss of the alveolar bone around the teeth, which results in the formation of pockets between gingiva and tooth which finally leads to loss of teeth. The aim of the present study was to develop Doxycycline Hyclate microspheres for periodontitis and then it is incorporated in to Carbomer gel in order to increase biocompatibility, bio adhesivity, allowing adhesion to the mucosa in the dental pocket and finally they can be rapidly eliminated through normal catabolic pathways, decreasing the risk of irritative or allergic host reactions at the application site. Pharmaceutical technologists today are able to provide drug delivery systems with very precise control over drug release for a prolonged period of time, dominating the need for a frequent dosing and minimizing side effects thereby increasing patient compliance and comfort. In conventional mode of administration, many drugs do not reach the target area in the body in sufficient concentration because many are prematurely inactivated and excreted. This problem can be overcome by administering the drugs directly into the intended site of action with lesser dose.

Key words: *Periodontitis, Doxycycline Hyclate, Microspheres, Drug delivery systems, Microorganisms.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Periodontal diseases are infections of the structures around the teeth. These include the gums, the cementum that covers the root, the periodontal ligament and the alveolar bone. In the earliest stage of periodontal disease, gingivitis, the infection affects only the gums. In more severe forms of the disease, all of the supporting tissues are involved. Periodontal disease is an infection that involves the inflammatory process and the immune response. A periodontal disease is known as a problem associated with an inflammatory response induced in a parodontium or periodontium by enzymes and toxic substances released from periodontal pathogens. The inflammatory response leads to progress of destruction of a pericemental membrane and absorption of an alveolar bone. As a pathologic condition of the periodontal disease, inflammation of gingival is observed at first. Then periodontal pocket is formed in the gingiva¹.

The major periodontal diseases are mucositis, gingivitis, periodontitis and dental caries. These diseases can be manifested by clinical signs such as bluish red thickened marginal gingiva, bluish red vertical zone from the gingival margin to the oral mucosa, gingival bleeding and localized pain. Drugs when taken orally or by intramuscular route, their concentration in blood increases and reaches a peak in few hours. The pharmacokinetics of the drug, i.e., absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion depends on the chemical structure of the drug. After reaching the peak blood level the drug then starts decreasing in concentration, hence must be re-administered when the concentration is thought to be reduced or close to the threshold for efficacy.

ANATOMY OF PERIODONTIUM

Structure of tooth

The tissues that surround and support the teeth are

collectively called the periodontium. Their main function is to support, protect and provide nourishment to the teeth. The word comes from greek terms peri- meaning “around” and odons meaning “tooth” literally taken it means that which is “around the tooth”. The periodontium has four components: gingiva, alveolar bone, periodontal ligament and the cementum².

Gingival

Gingival are part of the soft tissue lining of the mouth. They surround the teeth and provide a seal around them, compared with the soft tissue linings of the lips and cheeks most of the gingival are tightly bound to the underlying bone and are designed to resist the fraction of food passing over them. The healthy gingival is usually coral pink. The gingival is divided anatomically into marginal, attached, and inter dental gingival.

Alveolar bone

That part of the maxilla and mandible that supports and protects the teeth is known as alveolar bone and an arbitrary boundary at the level of the root apices separates alveolar bone from the body of maxilla and mandible. Alveolar bone has its embryological origin from the initial condensation of ectomesenchyme around the early tooth germ.

Periodontal ligament

The periodontal ligament, commonly abbreviated as the PDL is a group of specialized connective tissue fibers that essentially attach a tooth to the alveolar bone within which it sits. These fibers help the tooth withstand the naturally substantial compressive forces which occur during chewing and remain embedded in the bone. Another function of the PDL is to serve as a source of proprioception, or sensory innervation, so that the brain can detect the forces being placed on the teeth and react accordingly. To achieve this end, there are pressure sensitive receptors within the PDL which allow the brain to discern the amount of force being placed on a tooth during chewing, for example. This is important because the exposed surface of the tooth, called enamel, has no such sensory receptors itself.

Cementum

Cementum is a specialized calcified substance covering the root of a tooth. Cementum is excreted by cells called cementoblasts within the root of the tooth and is thickest at the root apex. Its coloration is yellowish and it is softer than enamel and dentin due to being less mineralized. Cementum's main role is to anchor the tooth by attaching it via the periodontal ligaments. It also plays an important role in forming new teeth. The chemical makeup of cementum is

similar to that of bone, but it lacks vascularization. Volumetrically, it is approximately 65% inorganic material (mainly hydroxyapatite), 23% organic material (mainly collagen type1) and 12% water.

PERIODONTITIS

The invisible, sticky film called plaque mainly composed of bacteria stays on the teeth for more than two or three days, can harden under the gumline into tartar (calculus). Tartar makes plaque more difficult to remove and acts as a reservoir for bacteria. Longer the plaque and tartar remain on the teeth, more the damage they cause. Initially irritation and inflammation occurs at the gingiva, which eventually causes pockets to develop between the gums and teeth that fill with plaque, tartar and bacteria. In time, these pockets become deeper and more bacteria accumulate, which causes infection and eventually leads to loss of tissue and bone^{3,4}.

The following are the most common symptoms of periodontal diseases.

- Bleeding gums during brushing.
- Red, swollen or tender gums.
- Gums that have pulled away from the teeth.
- Persistent bad breath.
- Pus between the teeth and gums.
- Loose or separating teeth.
- A change in the way your teeth fit together when you bite.

Comparison of healthy tooth and periodontitis

TYPES OF PERIODONTITIS

a. Mild Periodontitis (Gingivitis)

Gingiva is red, shiny, swollen and soft, or spongy in texture. The gums begin to separate from the teeth, forming pockets, which fill with plaque. Toxins produced by the bacteria in plaque irritate the gums. Patients suffering from gingivitis will have a pocket depth of 3 mm.

b. Moderate Periodontitis

Deeper pockets form as more bone and tissue are lost. The toxins stimulate a chronic inflammatory response in which the body in essence turns on itself and the tissues and bone that support the teeth are broken down and destroyed. It is characterized by puffy, bleeding gums with a pocket depth of up to 5 mm and early stages of bone loss⁵.

c. Advanced Periodontitis

This is a major state of Periodontitis. It is characterized by swollen, bleeding gums, more bone loss, gum recession and a pocket depth up to 6 mm or over which is harder to treat. Teeth may become loose because a large amount of bone and tissue have been lost. Further destruction occurred and could lead to the loss of teeth due to poor support.

d. Refractory Periodontitis

This stage can usually result in tooth loss because the major amount of bone is lost due to the excessive destruction of the bone and tissue, which are supporting to the teeth. Periodontal disease can and does occur in all groups, ethnicities, races, genders and socioeconomic levels. Periodontitis is a disease associated with periodontium in which irreversible step of loss of attachment occurs. Periodontitis develops in specific site; it does not occur in everyone with uncontrolled dental plaque, on all the teeth of susceptible or on all the surfaces of these teeth. Supportive periodontal therapy such as scaling, root planning and surgeries are common methods of treatment. Reoccurrence is not uncommon, even in well-maintained root planning and daily oral hygiene practice^{6,7}.

MICROORGANISMS ASSOCIATED WITH PERIODONTAL INFECTIONS.

The oral cavity is colonized by more than 400 species of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. Anaerobic bacteria outnumber their aerobic counterparts by a ratio of 10:1 to 100:1. These organisms inhabit the teeth, the gingival crevice, the mucous membranes, the dorsum of the tongue and saliva.

Microorganisms associated with Endodontal and Periodontal infections

AEROBIC AND FACULTATIVE ANAEROBIC BACTERIA	ANAEROBIC BACTERIA
<p><u>Gram-positive cocci</u> Streptococcus spp B-haemolytic streptococci Streptococcus milleri group Streptococcus mutans group</p> <p><u>Gram –positive bacilli</u> Rothia dentocariosa Lactobacillus sp Staphylococci</p> <p><u>Gram-negative cocco-bacilli</u> Actinobacillus spp Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans Campylobacter spp Campylobacter rectus Capnocytophaga spp Eikenella spp</p> <p><u>Gram-negative rods</u> Pseudomonas spp</p> <p><u>Gram-negative rods</u> Pseudomonas spp</p>	<p><u>Gram-positive cocci</u> Peptostreptococcus spp Peptostreptococcus micros</p> <p><u>Gram-negative bacilli</u> Veillonella spp</p> <p><u>Gram-positive bacilli</u> Actinomyces spp Eubacterium spp Propionibacterium spp Lactobacillus spp</p> <p><u>Spirochetes</u> Treponema denticola Treponema socranskii</p> <p><u>Gram-negative bacilli</u> Prevotella spp Prevotella intermedia Prevotella nigrescens Porphyromonas spp Porphyromonas gingivalis</p>

DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL INFECTIONS**1. Microspheres**

These are controlled release drug delivery system which comprises of drug-containing microparticles or microspheres, less than 200 microns in size, suspended in a pharmaceutically acceptable carrier medium, and are capable of maintaining an effective level of drug in the periodontal pocket for a period of one to thirty days. Non-biodegradable as well as biodegradable materials have been investigated for the preparation of microspheres. Microparticles based system of biodegradable poly alpha hydroxy acids such as poly lactide (PLA) or poly (lactide – co-glycolide) PLGA containing tetracycline has been designed for periodontal disease therapy. PLGA microspheres containing minocycline have been formulated and have been used for the elimination of Porphyromonas gingivalis from the periodontal pocket⁸.

2. Injectable Gels

Together with the solid devices, semisolid formulations also receive reasonable attention for the localised delivery of antibiotics. Semisolid or gel

formulations can indeed have some advantages. In spite of the relatively faster release of the incorporated drug, gels can be more easily prepared and administered. Moreover, they possess a higher biocompatibility and bioadhesivity, allowing adhesion to the mucosa in the dental pocket and, finally, they can be rapidly eliminated through normal catabolic pathways, decreasing the risk of irritative or allergic host reactions at the application site.

3. Fibers

Fibers, or thread-like devices, are reservoir-type systems, placed circumferentially into the pockets with an applicator and secured with cyanoacrylate adhesive for the sustained release of then trapped drug into the periodontal pocket. Several polymers such as poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), polyurethane, polypropylene, cellulose acetate propionate and ethyl vinyl acetate (EVA) have been investigated as matrices for the delivery of drug to the periodontal pocket.

4. Films

A far more widely used form of intra-pocket delivery device has been in the shape of film, prepared either by solvent casting or direct milling. Films are matrix

delivery systems in which drugs are distributed throughout the polymer and release occurs by drug diffusion and/or matrix dissolution or erosion. The advantages of such a device include ease of insertion, dimensions that confirms well with the dimensions of the pocket and minimum pain on insertion.

5.Injectable System

Injectable systems are particularly attractive for the delivery of antibiotic agents into the periodontal pocket. The application can be easily and rapidly carried out, without pain, by using a syringe. Thus, the cost of the therapy is considerably reduced compared to devices that need time to be placed and secured^{9,10}. Moreover, an injectable delivery system should be able to fill the pocket, thus reaching a large proportion of pathogens. These systems allow easy application of therapeutic agent using a syringe. They are also cost saving.

6.Strips and Compacts

Acrylic strips have been fabricated using a mixture of polymers, monomers and different concentrations of ant microbial agents. Strips were fabricated either by solvent casting or pressure melt method.

7.Vesicular Systems

Vesicular liposomal systems are designed to mimic the bio-membranes in terms of structure and bio-behaviour, and hence are investigated intensively for targeting periodontal biofilms.

8.Nanoparticulate System

Modern drug delivery systems are designed for targeted controlled slow drug release.The nanoparticulate system provides several advantages including high dispersibility in an aqueous medium, controlled release rate and increased stability. Nanoparticles, owing to their small size, penetrate regions that may be inaccessible to other delivery systems, such as the periodontal pocket areas below the gum line. These systems reduce the frequency of administration and further provide a uniform distribution of the active agent over an extended period of time. Biocompatible nanoparticles composed of 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) and polyethyleneglycol dimethacrylate (PEGDMA) could be used as a drug delivery system for dental applications¹¹.

MATERIALS USED IN THE STUDY

Sl.No.	Material	Grade	Suppliers
1	Doxycycline Hyclate IP	Pharma	Sangrose Laboratories,Kerala
2	Chitosan	L.R	Central Institute of Fisheries Technology,Cochin
3	Carbopol	L.R	Chemdyes corporation,Rajkot
4	Gluteraldehyde	L.R	Nice chemicals Pvt Ltd,Cochin
5	Glacial Acetic Acid	L.R	Nice chemicals Pvt Ltd,Cochin
6	Light Liquid paraffin	L.R	Nice chemicals Pvt Ltd,Cochin
7	Heavy Liquid Paraffin	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
8	Span 80	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
9	Acetone	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
10	Petroleum Ether	L.R	Cimson
11	Potassium dihydrogen Orthophosphate	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
12	Sodium Hydroxide	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
13	Toluene	L.R	Nice chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
14	Sodium metabisulphate	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
15	Triethanolamine	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin
16	Tween 80	L.R	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin

EQUIPMENTS USED IN THE STUDY

SL.NO.	NAME	MANUFACTURER
1	Electronic weighing Balance	AY 120 Shimadzu, Japan.
2	FT –IR spectrophotometer	SHIMADZU A213748
3	Double beam UV spectrometer	Shimadzu- UV 1800 ,Japan
4	Scanning Electron Microscope	JEOL JSM 6390, England
5	Mechanical stirrer	Remi Motors, Mumbai
6	Magnetic stirrer	Remi equipments Mumbai
7	Digital pH meter	Systronics MKV 1.
8	Melting point apparatus	Raaza Mumbai
9	Optical microscope	Olympus.
10	Haake digital viscosity tester model VT -550	IHS Engineering Laboratories USA
11	Dissolution Apparatus	Electrolab-TDT-06l

METHODS**PREFORMULATION STUDIES**

Preformulation testing is the first stage in the rationale development of dosage form of a drug substance. It is defined as the investigation of physical and chemical properties of drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. It gives extensive information to bring out good quality at high standard at which optimal dosage desired. Preformulation studies were performed on the drug (Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient), which included melting point determination, solubility and compatibility studies.

IDENTIFICATION OF THE DRUG**A) Identification by physicochemical parameters****a. Organoleptic properties**

The physical appearance of the drug was observed and compared with the pharmacopoeial specifications.

b. Solubility study

Solubility of the drug was observed in solvents like water, methanol, ethanol. Chloroform etc.

B) Identification by melting point

Melting point of pure doxycycline hyclate was determined by open capillary method. The capillary tube was closed at one end by fusion and was filled with doxycycline hyclate by repeated tapings. The capillary tube was then placed in a melting point apparatus. The temperature at which the drug started to melt was recorded. This was performed thrice and the average value was calculated¹².

C) Identification by FTIR spectroscopy

FTIR spectral analysis of the pure drug was carried out. The absorption maxima in the spectrum were compared with the reference spectrum.

D) Identification by DSC Study

DSC thermogram of the drug was recorded out for the identification purpose. The melting point of the sample was noted.

IDENTIFICATION OF POLYMERS**A). Physicochemical parameters****a. Organoleptic parameters of polymers**

The physical properties of polymers were recorded and compared with the official specifications.

b. Solubility study

The solubility profiles of the polymers in various solvent systems were recorded.

B. Identification of the polymers by FTIR spectroscopy

FTIR spectral analysis of the polymers was carried out. The absorption maxima in the spectrum were compared with the reference spectrum.¹³

ANALYTICAL METHODS**A) Determination of λ max****Procedure:**

The λ max of Doxycycline Hyclate was determined in phosphate buffer P^H6.6. Doxycycline Hyclate was dissolved in buffer and the UV absorption spectra were taken after suitable dilutions. The wavelength which shows maximum absorption was taken as the λ max of drug with respect to the media.

B) Development of standard curve of Doxycycline Hyclate

Procedure:

100mg of Doxycycline Hyclate was accurately weighed and quantitatively transferred to a 100ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved and made up to 100ml with phosphate buffer of P^H 6.6, so as to obtain a solution of 1mg/ml (1000 μ g/ml). 1ml of this stock solution was again diluted to 100ml with buffer to obtain 10 μ g/ml solution. Volumes of 2,4,6,8,10ml of this solution were separately pipetted out and diluted with buffer in 10ml volumetric flask to obtain standard solutions of 2,4,6,8,10 μ g/ml. The absorbance of these solutions were recorded at 274nm and a graph was plotted with concentration against absorbance¹⁴.

Preparation of phosphate buffer pH 6.6

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate 0.2 M : Dissolved 27.218 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in distilled water and volume adjusted to produce 1000 ml.

Sodium hydroxide 0.2 M : 8 g of NaOH was dissolved in distilled water and volume adjusted to produce 1000 ml.

PREPARATION OF MICROSPHERES

The chitosan microspheres were prepared by **Emulsion Cross Linking Method**¹⁵

METHOD A

Chitosan solution was prepared in 1% acetic acid solution by overnight stirring in a magnetic stirrer. The drug was dispersed in this solution and mixed well. 3ml of the above mixture was injected through a syringe (No.23) into 20 ml of oil phase containing Span 80 (1ml) and stirring was performed by mechanical stirrer at 2000 rpm to form water in oil emulsion. Oil phase was a mixture of heavy and light liquid paraffin in 1:1 ratio. The stirring was then continued for a period of 30 minutes.

METHOD B

Weighed amount of chitosan was dissolved in 1% acetic acid. Tween- 80 was added at a concentration of 2%v/v. Drug was then added to the above solution and mixed well to obtain a uniform dispersion. 3ml of the above solution was injected to a mixture of 20ml heavy liquid paraffin and 1ml of span-80 while stirring at a speed of 2000rpm. The stirring was continued for 30minutes to obtain a w/o emulsion.

After the specified homogenization period for both the method 1ml of gluteraldehyde saturated toluene (GST) was added in frequent time intervals of 10minutes and stirring continued for 3hours for cross linking of chitosan. The solidified microspheres were collected by centrifugation, washed 3 times with petroleum ether and 3 times with acetone in order to remove oil and gluteraldehyde. The resultant microspheres were dried in a hot air oven at 40 $^{\circ}$ c.

Formulation table for Doxycycline Hyclate loaded chitosan microspheres.

METHOD A			METHOD B		
CODE	AMOUNT OF DRUG (mg)	DRUG: POLYMER	CODE	AMOUNT OF DRUG (mg)	DRUG: POLYMER
AC1	20	1:1	BC1	20	1:1
AC2	20	1:2	BC2	20	1:2
AC3	20	1:4	BC3	20	1:4
AC4	20	1:5	BC4	20	1:5
AC5	20	1:6	BC5	20	1:6
AC6	20	1:10	BC6	20	1:10
AC7	20	1:15	BC7	20	1:15
AC8	20	1:20	BC8	20	1:20

EVALUATION OF CHITOSAN MICROSPHERES

Percentage Yield of microspheres

The percentage yield was found out for all the formulations based on the dry weight of drug and polymers taken. The percentage yield was calculated using the equation,

$$\text{Percentage Yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of microspheres/}}{\text{Weight of polymer and drug fed initially}} \times 100$$

Percentage Entrapment Efficiency

Microspheres equivalent to 20mg of Doxycycline were crushed in a glass mortar and pestle and the powdered microspheres were suspended in 100ml of phosphate buffer of pH 6.6. After 24h, the solution was filtered, 1ml of the filtrate was pipette out and diluted to 25ml and analyzed for the drug content using UV Visible spectrophotometer at 274nm.¹⁶

The drug entrapment was calculated as per the following formula,

$$\% \text{Drug Entrapment Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Practical Drug Content}}{\text{Theoretical Drug Content}} \times 100$$

Particle Size Analysis

The particle sizes of the microspheres were determined by Optical microscopy method. The eye piece was calibrated using the stage micrometers. The microspheres were mounted on to the slide and the sizes of hundred particles were counted in various areas focused.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The surface morphology of the microspheres were determined by Scanning electron microscopy using a JEOL JSM – 6390 scanning microscope. Dry microspheres were placed on an electron microscope brass stub and coated with platinum in an ion sputter. Picture of microspheres were taken by random scanning of the stub.

Swelling Ratio Study

The swelling ratio of microspheres was determined by immersion in a phosphate buffered saline (PBS) of pH 6.6 at room temperature for 24 hr with gentle shaking. Subsequently the weight of swollen microspheres (W_{sw}) was measured and the swelling ratio (E_{sw}) was calculated according to the equation,

$$E_{sw} = \frac{(W_{sw} - W_o)}{W_o} \times 100$$

E_{sw} \longrightarrow Swelling Ratio
 W_{sw} \longrightarrow Weight of swollen microspheres
 W_o \longrightarrow Initial weight of microspheres

In – vitro Dissolution Studies

In – vitro drug release from different formulations was investigated in PBS pH6.6. The drug release studies

were carried out in USP Type I Dissolution Apparatus with slight modifications. Microspheres (20mg) were suspended in 1ml of PBS pH6.6 and placed within a dialysis bag. The sample within a dialysis bag was kept in a beaker containing 50ml of PBS as the dissolution medium and it was stirred at 50rpm. The beaker was covered with aluminium foil in order to avoid the light interactions. The whole assembly was maintained at 37°C using a thermostatic water bath. The amount of drug released was determined by withdrawing each time 1ml aliquots at the selected specific time intervals. The volume withdrawn was replenished with an equal volume of fresh and prewarmed PBS at 37°C. Samples were analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at the λ_{max} value 274nm using PBS as the blank. All dissolution studies were performed in triplicate. The values were plotted as percentage cumulative drug release against time.

Diagrammatic representation of In vitro dissolution study

FORMULATION OF DOXYCYCLINE HYCLATE MICROSPHERE LOADED GEL PROCEDURE

Accurately weighed 400mg of carbopol was dissolved in 15ml of water. Chitosan microspheres loaded with 100mg of Doxycycline Hyclate was added to the drug carbopol solution and mixed well. Various ingredients viz. sodium Meta bisulphate, Methyl hydroxyl benzoate were added to the microsphere drug, carbopol mixture. Finally, Triethanolamine was added to produce gel and volume was made with water.

Various ingredients used in formulation of gel are mentioned,

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION (%W/W)
Doxycycline Hyclate(equivalent to)	100mg
Carbopol 934	400mg
Methyl Hydroxybenzoate	0.15
Propyl Hydroxybenzoate	0.05
Sodium Metabisulphate	0.1
Triethanolamine	0.33ml
Water	QS up to 15g

EVALUATION OF MICROSPHERE LOADED GEL

Gels were evaluated for their Homogeneity p^H , Viscosity, Drug content, Syringeability study, *In - vitro* drug release studies and antimicrobial susceptibility test¹⁷.

Homogeneity

All developed gels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection after the gels have been set in the container for their appearance and presence of any aggregate.

pH

1gram of gel was accurately weighed and dispersed in 100 ml of distilled water. The pH of dispersion was measured by using digital pH meter.

Viscosity measurement

The Haake digital viscosity tester (model VT -550, IHS Engineering Laboratories USA) was used to measure the viscosity (in cps) of the prepared gel formulations.

Haake Digital Viscosity Tester

Drug content

Gel containing 1mg of drug was taken in 10ml volumetric flask, dissolved in pH 6.6 phosphate buffer

made up the volume to 10ml with pH 6.6 phosphate buffer and then filtered. All the precautions were taken in order to avoid light interactions. Absorbance values were measured at λ_{max} 274nm. Concentrations of drug were calculated from the standard calibration curve prepared in pH 6.6 phosphate buffer.

Syringeability Study

Syringeability study was carried out by using a 22 gauge needle.

In vitro diffusion study of microsphere loaded gel formulations

The *in -vitro* release of Doxycycline Hyclate and Doxycycline Hyclate microsphere from the formulations was studied through cellophane membrane using an open end cylinder. The medium used was freshly prepared phosphate buffer p^H 6.6. Cellophane membrane, previously soaked overnight in the dissolution medium, was tied to one end of a specifically designed glass cylinder (open at both ends and of 5 cm diameter). The formulation was accurately weighed and placed in membrane and attached to this assembly. The cylinder was attached to the metallic driveshaft and suspended in 50 ml of dissolution medium maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ C$ so that the membrane just touched the receptor medium surface. The medium was stirred at 50 rpm using magnetic stirrer. Aliquots, each of 1ml volume, were withdrawn at hourly intervals and replaced by an equal volume of the receptor medium. The aliquots were diluted with the receptor medium and analyzed by UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 274 nm. All the precautions were taken in order to avoid light interactions.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test

Aseptically prepared gel formulation was used in microbial assay. Inoculum was made by transferring *Staphylococcus aureus* into 10 ml nutrient broth. Sterile melted nutrient agar was cooled and, 1 ml *S. aureus* inoculum was put into a sterile petri dish and 20 ml agar was poured into it. The inoculated agar was well-mixed and left to solidify. Two wells were bored using a sterile cork on two sides of the solid inoculated agar. 60 μ l of the formulated gels (Pure gel and Microsphere loaded gel) were put into the well. The inoculated agar was incubated at $37^\circ C$ for 24 hours, then the zone of inhibition was measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

IDENTIFICATION OF DRUG

A). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETRES

I. Organoleptic Parameters Doxycycline Hyclate was found to be light yellow crystalline powder. The physical appearance complied with reference specification.

II. Solubility

Solubility profile of drug

Drug	Water	Ethanol	Methanol	Chloroform
Doxycycline Hyclate	Freely soluble	Sparingly soluble	Freely soluble	Insoluble

The Doxycycline Hyclate was found to be insoluble in chloroform, sparingly soluble in ethanol, and freely soluble in water and methanol.

B). IDENTIFICATION BY MELTING POINT DETERMINATION

The melting point of Doxycycline was found to be 205°C

Experimental value was found to be in good agreement with the official value which indicated the purity of the sample. If any impurity is present, it will cause variation in the melting point of given substance. The melting point of sample was complied with IP standards, thus confirmed the purity of given samples.

C). IDENTIFICATION BY FTIR SPECTROSCOPY

The IR spectrum of Doxycycline was recorded by FTIR spectrometer and shown in following figure and compared with standard functional group frequencies.

The IR spectrum showed the characteristic group frequencies of Doxycycline hence the given drug sample identified as the Doxycycline.

Fig IR spectra of Doxycycline Hyclate

Interpretation of FTIR Spectrum

Major functional groups present in Doxycycline were shown characteristics peaks in FTIR spectrum. The characteristic peaks of Doxycycline were obtained at 1576.90 cm⁻¹, 3288.96 cm⁻¹, 1218.75 cm⁻¹, 1331.29 cm⁻¹, 1360.34 cm⁻¹, 1613 cm⁻¹, 3325 cm⁻¹. The major peaks were identical to functional group of Doxycycline. Hence the sample was confirmed as Doxycycline.

ANALYTICAL METHODS

A. Determination of λ_{max}

The λ_{max} of Doxycycline Hyclate was determined by scanning the 10 µg/ml solution of the drug in Phosphate buffer pH 6.6 using UV-Spectrophotometer and was found to be 274 nm.

B. Development of Calibration curve of Doxycycline Hyclate

A standard calibration curve for the drug was obtained by measuring absorbance at 274 nm and by plotting the graph of absorbance Vs concentration

Data for calibration curve of Doxycycline at 274 nm

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 274nm
0	0
2	0.062
4	0.132
6	0.198
8	0.254
10	0.319

Graph :Calibration Curve of Doxycycline Hyclate in PBS p^{H} 6.6 at 274nm

PREPARATION OF DOXYCYCLINE HYCLATE LOADED CHITOSAN MICROSPHERES

Drug loaded chitosan microspheres were successfully prepared by **Emulsion Cross Linking Method**. The obtained microspheres were yellowish brown colored free flowing particles.Prepared formulations were subjected to evaluation.

Fig: Formulated Doxycycline loaded chitosan microspheres

EVALUATION OF CHITOSAN MICROSPHERES

Percentage Yield

Percentage yield of all prepared microsphere formulations were determined and the results were given in Table.

Table : Percentage Yield Of Microspheres

Sl.No	Formulations	%Yield	Sl.No	Formulations	%Yield
1	AC1	67.01±0.19	9	BC1	68.04±0.03
2	AC2	70.16±0.09	10	BC2	75.56±0.06
3	AC3	72.85±0.19	11	BC3	75.71±0.11
4	AC4	75.50±0.33	12	BC4	85.71±0.12
5	AC5	80.12±0.08	13	BC5	88.57±0.34
6	AC6	81.22±0.14	14	BC6	89.05±0.11
7	AC7	88.63±0.33	15	BC7	92.45±0.04
8	AC8	82.35±0.32	16	BC8	88.19±0.07

Entrapment Efficiency

Amount of drug entrapped in chitosan microspheres of Doxycycline Hyclate was estimated and is reported in Table 12. The entrapment efficiency was found in between 76.08%-90.87% and 80.21-98.83% for method A and method B respectively.

Table 12 : Entrapment efficiency of Microspheres

Sl.No	Formulations	%Entrapment	Sl.No	Formulations	%Entrapment
1	AC1	76.08±0.19	9	BC1	80.21±0.17
2	AC2	78.10±0.39	10	BC2	83.29±0.12
3	AC3	78.32±0.25	11	BC3	89.02±0.35
4	AC4	80.64±0.42	12	BC4	90.90±0.16
5	AC5	80.90±0.06	13	BC5	92.14±0.45
6	AC6	83.14±0.48	14	BC6	95.20±0.24
7	AC7	90.87±0.11	15	BC7	98.83±0.05
8	AC8	87.65±0.30	16	BC8	97.11±0.22

OPTIMIZATION OF THE BEST FORMULA

BC7 is selected as the best formulation based on the entrapment efficiency, swelling ratio, and *in vitro* release. When method A and method B was compared, method B showed better results. Out of 8 formulations prepared by method B, BC7 shows better result, so it is selected as the best formulation and was chosen for further studies.

6.6. FORMULATION OF CARBOPOL GEL OF DOXYCYCLINE HYCLATE AND DOXYCYCLINE HYCLATE MICROSPHERES

Formulations of Doxycycline Hyclate and Doxycycline Hyclate microsphere gel was developed using carbopol 934, methyl hydroxybenzoate, propyl hydroxybenzoate, sodium metabisulphate, triethanolamine and water. Carbopol 934 was used as the polymer, methyl paraben and propyl paraben as preservative, triethanolamine is added as a neutralizer, it can neutralize carbomer to enable it to thicken in to gel, and water as vehicle.

EVALUATION OF PERIODONTAL GEL FORMULATIONS

Evaluation parameter of gel formulation

Formulation	Homogeneity	pH	Viscosity(cps)	Syringeability
Pure DXY gel	Good	6.3	1250	Syringeable
DXY microsphere loaded gel(BC7)	Good	6.5	1300	Syringeable

Drug content Estimation

Gels were evaluated for their Homogeneity, pH, Viscosity, Drug content, syringeability study, *in vitro* diffusion studies and antimicrobial susceptibility test by using standard procedure.

Homogeneity

Developed formulation showed good homogeneity with absence of lumps.

pH

The pH value of developed formulation of Carbopol gel was found to be 6.5 this indicates the formulation can be used without any irritation in the oral cavity.

Viscosity measurement

The viscosity of various formulated Doxycycline hyclate gels were measured using Digital Haake viscosity tester. The rheological behavior of all formulated gel was studied.

Syringeability Study

The results of the syringeability study indicate that all the gel formulations were syringeable through 22 gauge needle.

After formulating Doxycycline hyclate gel and microsphere (BC7) loaded gel, the drug content of the formulated gels were estimated by UV spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 274nm. The percentage drug content of all prepared gel formulations were found to be 93.72% and 98.86%.

Drug content of formulated periodontal gel

Formulation	%DrugContent
Pure Doxycycline hyclate gel	93.72±0.62
Doxycycline Microsphere(BC7) loaded gel	98.86±0.30

In vitro diffusion study of microsphere loaded gel formulations

The release profiles obtained for the Doxycycline Hyclate microsphere(BC7) loaded gel formulation & Pure Doxycycline gel are represented in Table . Cumulative release for the microsphere loaded gel after 120 hrs was about 98.43 %. In case of pure gel drug get released maximum after 48hrs.

In vitro drug release studies of Pure DXY gel and Microsphere loaded gel

Time (hrs)	%Cumulative drug release profile of pure DXY gel	%Cumulative drug release profile of DXY microsphere loaded gel
0	0	0
2	18.81±0.41	7.68±0.27
4	29.14±0.15	18.09±0.40
6	42.09±0.30	29.09±0.28
8	58.30±0.27	32.90±0.17
10	68.08±0.09	41.90±0.50
12	77.54±0.43	51.01±0.19
24	86.13±0.15	65.14±0.17
48	99.86±0.21	77.21±0.33
72	-	90.65±0.24
96	-	96.76±0.37
120	-	98.43±0.12

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test

The results of the antimicrobial studies of the formulated DXY microsphere loaded gel against *Staphylococcus aureus* using agar diffusion method (well method) is shown on Figure00, and the diameter of zone of inhibition is shown on Table. The formulation showed excellent zone of inhibition after 1 day incubation at 37°C. Davis and Stout has classified the strength of antimicrobial activity in agar diffusion method based on the zone of inhibition. If the zone of inhibition less than 0.5 cm, the inhibition activity is weak. If the zone of inhibition is 0.5-1 cm, the inhibition activity is moderate. If the zone of inhibition is 1-1.9 cm, the inhibition activity is strong. If the zone of inhibition is 2.0 cm or larger, the inhibition activity is excellent. Antibacterial activity of the formulation against *S. aureus* in 1 day observation period was concluded as excellent.

Figure Antimicrobial Activity of DXY microsphere(BC7) loaded gel against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Result of antimicrobial Study

Sl No.	Organism	Formulation	Zone of inhibition(cm)
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	DXYmicrosphere(BC7) loaded gel	4.9
2	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Pure DXY gel	4.7

KINETIC MODELING

The results obtained of *in vitro* release studies were attempted to fit into various mathematical models as follows:

- **Zero order rate kinetics** Cumulative percent drug released Vs. Time
- **First order kinetics** Log Cumulative percent drug released Vs. Time
- **Higuchi matrix** Cumulative percent released Vs. square root of Time
- **Korsmeyer Peppas** Log cumulative percent drug released Vs. Log Time

Release kinetics of Doxycycline Hyclate Microsphere (BC7) loaded Gel

Data obtained from *in vitro* study was fitted into various kinetic models such as Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas. The regression coefficient (r) of zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas are tabulated in Table:

Kinetic release profile of Doxycycline Hyclate microsphere (BC7) loaded gel

Time (hrs)	Root Time	Log Time	% CDR	Log %CDR	%Drug retained	Log %Drug retained
0	0	#NUM!	0	#NUM!	100	2
2	1.414214	0.30103	7.68	0.885361	92.32	1.965295796
4	2	0.60206	18.09	1.257439	81.91	1.913336926
6	2.44949	0.778151	29.07	1.463445	70.93	1.85082996
8	2.828427	0.90309	32.9	1.517196	67.1	1.82672252
10	3.162278	1	41.8	1.621176	58.2	1.764922985
12	3.464102	1.079181	51.01	1.707655	48.99	1.690107439
24	4.898979	1.380211	65.14	1.813848	34.86	1.542327383
48	6.928203	1.681241	77.21	1.887674	22.79	1.357744325
72	8.485281	1.857332	90.65	1.957368	9.35	0.970811611
96	9.797959	1.982271	96.76	1.985696	3.24	0.51054501
120	10.95445	2.079181	98.43	1.993127	1.57	0.195899652

Plots of Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas are depicted in Graph00-00. The regression coefficient (r) of zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Peppas are tabulated in Table:

Figure: Zero Order Plot for microsphere loaded gel.

Figure: First order plot for microsphere loaded gel

Figure: Higuchi plot of microsphere loaded gel

Figure: Korsmeyer Peppas plot for microsphere loaded gel

Model fitting for the release profile of Doxycycline hyclate microsphere(BC7) loaded gel by using 4 different models

Formulation	Correlation co-efficient (R ²) value			
	Zero Order	First Order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer Peppas
Microsphere (BC4)loaded gel	0.873	0.389	0.943	0.799
				Diffusion exponent (n) n= 0.770

Plots of zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix, Peppas model are depicted in graph . The regression coefficient (r) values of zero order, first order, Higuchi model, peppas model are tabulated in Table for microsphere(BC7) loaded gel formulation. From the table, it is clear that the drug release shows Higuchi matrix model for the formulation. Hence the drug release mechanism was assumed to be 'diffusion controlled'. When analysed according to Peppas model, the release exponent was found to be 0.770. Therefore the diffusional release was found to follow non-Fickian diffusion.

CONCLUSION:

The present study has been a satisfactory attempt to formulate Doxycycline Hyclate microsphere loaded gel for periodontitis, with a view to produce a local delivery system of Doxycycline, which is used for the prolonged therapy for periodontitis. The release profile of the Doxycycline microspheres (BC7) loaded carbopol periodontal gel was compared with that of the pure Doxycycline gel. From the result it can be concluded that the sphere loaded gel release the drug slowly over a period of 120 hrs. When compared to the 99.86% releases at the end of 48hrs from the pure Doxycycline gel. This local drug delivery formulation is a viable alternative to systemic antibiotic therapy by virtue of its ability to increase the drug concentration at the site of action and release drug for a prolonged period. By model fitting of the data obtained by drug release profile we can conclude that the mechanism of drug release from microspheres (BC7) gel was non-Fickian and it follows Higuchi matrix model. Also important is its ease of administration, reduced side effects and reduced frequency of administration resulting in better patient acceptance.

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